

Original Research Article

Image-based quantification of mitochondrial iron uptake via Mitoferrin-2

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ABSTRACT

Iron is a trace element that is critical for most living organisms and plays a key role in a wide variety of metabolic processes. In the mitochondrion, iron is involved in producing iron-sulfur clusters and synthesis of heme and kept within physiological ranges by concerted activity of multiple molecules. Mitochondrial iron uptake is mediated by the solute carrier transporters Mitoferrin-1 (SLC25A37) and Mitoferrin-2 (SLC25A28). While Mitoferrin-1 is mainly involved in erythropoiesis, the cellular function of the ubiquitously expressed Mitoferrin-2 remains less well defined. Furthermore, Mitoferrin-2 is associated with several human diseases, including cancer, cardiovascular and metabolic diseases, hence representing a potential therapeutic target. Here, we developed a robust approach to quantify mitochondrial iron uptake mediated by Mitoferrin-2 in living cells. We utilize HEK293 cells with inducible expression of Mitoferrin-2 and measure iron-induced quenching of rhodamine B[(1,10-phenanthroline-5-yl)-aminocarbonyl]benzyl ester (RPA) fluorescence and validate this assay for medium-throughput screening. This assay may allow identification and characterization of Mitoferrin-2 modulators and could enable drug discovery for this target.

1. Introduction

Iron is an essential element for a variety of body functions (Ganz, 2013; Yiannikourides and Latunde-Dada, 2019) and has major functions in mitochondrial metabolism (Paul et al., 2017). Mitochondrial iron sustains production of iron-sulfur clusters and synthesis of heme, pathways in which defects underly human disease etiology (Campuzano et al., 1996; Cazzola et al., 2003; Farhan et al., 2014; Kollberg et al., 2009; Miller et al., 2011; Ye et al., 2010). Extracellular iron is taken up in mammalian cells through transferrin receptor-mediated endocytosis and facilitated diffusion mediated by solute carrier transporters (SLCs) (Ganz, 2013; Yiannikourides and Latunde-Dada, 2019). Following cellular uptake, cytosolic labile iron is transported to the mitochondria by the redundantly expressed SLCs Mitoferrin-1 (SLC25A37) and Mitoferrin-2 (SLC25A28) (Hung et al., 2013; Paradkar et al., 2009). The activity of these two transporters is therefore critical for maintaining mitochondrial iron homeostasis. Whilst Mitoferrin-1 is particularly important for erythropoiesis (Shaw et al., 2006; Troadec et al., 2011),

the precise role of Mitoferrin-2 in human physiology remains controversial (Ali et al., 2022; Seguin et al., 2020). The abundant expression of Mitoferrin-2 throughout the body potentially reflects its importance for mitochondrial function across a variety of tissues (Uhlen et al., 2015). Moreover, a substantial amount of preclinical evidence and human genetic studies suggest a role for Mitoferrin-2 in the pathophysiology of cancer (Law et al., 2019; Ni et al., 2020), atherosclerosis (Wang et al., 2021), and rare genetic diseases (Martelli and Puccio, 2014). Thus, modulation of Mitoferrin-2 activity may be a potential therapeutic opportunity. Presently, no functional assay specific for Mitoferrin-2 has been described in the literature. Therefore, it is currently not possible to screen libraries of compounds for identification of modulators of Mitoferrin-2 activity.

In this study, we engineered human embryonic kidney 293 (HEK293) cells to inducibly express functional mitochondrial Mitoferrin-2. Using this cell line, we established a novel cell-based fluorometric assay that measures mitochondrial iron uptake mediated by Mitoferrin-2. This robust functional assay shows a high signal-to-noise ratio,

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reproducibility, and amenability to medium-throughput screening. Our methodology presented here may enable the discovery of modulators of Mitoferrin-2, facilitating future drug discovery on this key therapeutic target.

2. Results

2.1. Generation and characterization of Mitoferrin-2-overexpressing HEK293 cells

First, we generated HEK293-JumpIn cells with doxycycline (DOX)-inducible C-terminal HA-tagged Mitoferrin-2 (HEK293-JI-Mitoferrin-2). To achieve an optimal assay window, we next isolated cell clones with high levels of Mitoferrin-2 from the HEK293-JI-Mitoferrin-2 pool. We selected a single clone (HEK293-JI-Mitoferrin-2-C1; HEKiM2) displaying more homogenous (94 % of cells; Fig. S1A) and higher (1.8-fold increase; Fig. S1B) expression of the transgene as compared to the parental pool. We further confirmed DOX-induced Mitoferrin-2 expression (Fig. S1C) and proper localization of expressed Mitoferrin-2 to mitochondria (Fig. S1D) in expanded HEKiM2 cells and used these cells throughout the study.

2.2. Quantification of Mitoferrin-2-mediated mitochondrial iron uptake by ICP-MS

To evaluate the activity of the overexpressed Mitoferrin-2 in HEKiM2 cells, we first quantified mitochondrial uptake of iron and other divalent metal ions by inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). To this end, mitochondrial fractions were enriched from HEKiM2 cells and incubated with $\text{Fe}(\text{II})\text{SO}_4$ containing both ^{58}Fe and ^{56}Fe stable iron isotopes (Fig. 1A). Analysis of divalent metal concentrations in mitochondria by ICP-MS revealed a 2.4-fold increase in concentration of both ^{58}Fe and ^{56}Fe upon induction of Mitoferrin-2 (Fig. 1B). We found no significant changes in the levels of other divalent metal ions (^{55}Mn , ^{63}Cu and ^{66}Zn ; Fig. 1C). This data demonstrate that the inducible Mitoferrin-2 is functional and specifically transports iron out of the tested divalent metals.

2.3. Image-based analyses of RPA fluorescence quenching for quantification of Mitoferrin-2-dependent mitochondrial iron uptake

To overcome the need for mitochondrial enrichment, which requires large numbers of cells and is therefore difficult to apply to a higher throughput format, we set up a complementary HEKiM2 cell-based 24-well assay. We based our assay on fluorescence of rhodamine B[(1,10-phenanthroline-5-yl)-aminocarbonyl]benzyl ester (RPA), a dye that accumulates in mitochondria. RPA fluorescence is quenched by chelatable iron (Petrat et al., 2002). Imaging of live HEKiM2 cells upon incubation with RPA confirmed mitochondrial localization of the dye (Fig. 2A). Incubation of doxycycline-induced (DOX+) HEKiM2 cells for 12 h in the presence of 100 μM $\text{Fe}(\text{II})\text{SO}_4$ resulted in reduction of mitochondrial RPA fluorescence compared to uninduced (DOX-) cells (Fig. 2B; left panel), indicating a Mitoferrin-2-dependent mitochondrial iron uptake. As doxycycline itself has an intrinsic capacity of chelating iron (Grenier et al., 2000), we assessed the effect of doxycycline addition without concurrent Mitoferrin-2 induction in non-transfected HEK293-JumpIn cells. As HEK293-JumpIn cells do not have doxycycline-inducible Mitoferrin-2 expression, we do not expect any affect of doxycycline administration, unless doxycycline itself acts as a chelator. Indeed, the RPA signal remained unchanged in HEK293-JumpIn cells independently of doxycycline addition in the presence of 100 μM of $\text{Fe}(\text{II})\text{SO}_4$ (Fig. 2B; right panel), confirming the specificity of Mitoferrin-2-mediated iron chelation in HEKiM2 cells expressing Mitoferrin-2 (Fig. 2B; left panel). As a next step we demonstrated the stability of RPA signal over time, demonstrating a sufficient time window for fluorescence measurement (Fig. 2C). Altogether, these results showed that quenching of RPA

Fig. 1. Iron is selectively transported into mitochondria upon Mitoferrin-2 induction. (A) Western blot analysis of the mitochondrial (mito.) and cytoplasmic fractions obtained by serial centrifugation of HEKiM2 cells. Cells were grown in media containing vehicle (DOX-) or 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ doxycycline (DOX+). 10 μg protein from each mitochondrial or cytosolic fraction was separated on a 4–12 % SDS-PAGE gel. Fractions were probed with cytosol- (P70-S6 kinase) and mitochondria-specific (citrate synthase) antibodies. (B–C) ^{58}Fe and ^{56}Fe (B) and ^{55}Mn , ^{63}Cu , and ^{66}Zn (C) concentrations in mitochondrial fractions of DOX- and DOX+ HEKiM2 cells as quantified by ICP-MS and normalized to sample protein concentrations. Horizontal line indicates the mean per group. N = 2 replicates were used per condition.

fluorescence can be used to quantify Mitoferrin-2-mediated iron transport into mitochondria of live cells.

2.4. Development and validation of a medium-throughput RPA-based imaging assay to quantify Mitoferrin-2-dependent mitochondrial iron uptake

We aimed to adapt the 24-well plate Mitoferrin-2 mitochondrial iron uptake assay described above to a 96-well format, to be applied to screening of Mitoferrin-2 modulators. Briefly, we set up a semi-automated image segmentation analysis protocol to measure mitochondrial RPA in DOX+ and DOX- HEKiM2 cells (Fig. 2D; details available in Materials and Methods). Comparison of various image analysis and segmentation strategies of the high-content imaging data displayed robustness of the assay (Fig. 2E). After this evaluation, a scanR software-based strategy was selected for further analyses due to its amenability to high-throughput screening. By optimizing cell culture conditions, we found that using serum-free growth medium increased the assay window and robustness as determined by Z-factor calculation (Z') (Fig. 2F). Our optimized assay showed an acceptable intra- and inter-plate reproducibility, across different cell passages (Fig. 2G). This

Fig. 2. Image-based analyses of RPA fluorescence quenching enables quantification of Mitoferrin-2-dependent mitochondrial iron import. (A) Mitochondrial localization of RPA signal in HEKIM2 cells. RPA signal (top) is found in punctate structures staining positive for MitoTracker Deep Red (bottom). (B) RPA signal in vehicle- (DOX-) and doxycycline-treated (DOX+) HEKIM2 (left) and HEK-JI-WT (right) cells. Cells were seeded into 24-well plates and incubated overnight with 100 μ M of Fe(II)SO₄. Dots represent mean intensity values of RPA fluorescence in 4 fields/well. N = 5, 6, 6, and 6 replicates for included conditions. p-values indicate Student's *t*-test significance: **** = $p < 0.0001$. (C) HEKIM2 RPA signal stability over time. HEKIM2 cells were grown in 6-well plates and RPA fluorescence was measured over the course of 50 min from start of imaging. Dots represent mean intensity values of RPA fluorescence in 4 fields/well with N = 3 replicates per time point with error bars indicating the SEM. $p < 0.05$ 2-WAY ANOVA RM. (D) Exemplary images of raw intensities (left) and Olympus scanR segmentation masks (right) of mitochondrial RPA signal. (E) Impact of image processing software on RPA readout. DOX- and DOX+ HEKIM2 cells plated in 96-well plates were incubated overnight with indicated Fe(II)SO₄ concentrations. Boxplots represent mean intensity values of RPA fluorescence for N = 9–12 replicates in 4 fields per well upon segmentation using indicated image analysis algorithms. Table indicates the fold decrease in RPA signal upon Mitoferrin-2 induction across the different conditions. p-values indicate Student's *t*-test significance: **** = $p < 0.0001$ and ** = $p < 0.01$. (F) Impact of fetal calf serum (FCS) on RPA variability. Boxplots represent segmented RPA signal as quantified with scanR in DOX- and DOX+ HEKIM2 cells upon overnight incubation in 96-well plates of N = 6–12 replicates with indicated Fe(II)SO₄ concentrations in normal (top) or FCS-deprived (bottom) medium. p-values indicate Student's *t*-test significance: **** = $p < 0.0001$ and *** = $p < 0.001$. (G) Robustness of RPA quantification across plates and cell line passages. N = 9 replicates of HEKIM2 cells of different passages were incubated with 100 μ M Fe(II)SO₄ and measured in different 96-well plates. Z' factor values are annotated. p-values indicate Student's *t*-test significance: **** = $p < 0.0001$.

robust 96-well plate-based assay could be used to quantify iron transport via Mitoferrin-2 and provides an opportunity to screen libraries of compounds for identification of Mitoferrin-2 modulators.

3. Discussion

Proteins of the solute carrier (SLC) family, such as Mitoferrin-2, ensure the maintenance of cellular and mitochondrial iron homeostasis. The lack of established medium- or high-throughput screening assays for assessment of Mitoferrin-2 activity is a major obstacle in initiating drug discovery programs for Mitoferrin-2. A great amount of evidence points to the potential of Mitoferrin-2 modulators for the treatment of not only diseases for which human genetic studies suggest a role for Mitoferrin-2 (Law et al., 2019; Martelli and Puccio, 2014; Ni et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2021), but also for pathologies characterized by mitochondrial iron accumulation, such as Friedreich's ataxia (Babcock et al., 1997; Farhan et al., 2014; Puccio et al., 2001; Yamamoto et al., 2014). In this study, we therefore developed a cell-based fluorometric assay for Mitoferrin-2-mediated mitochondrial iron transport and demonstrated its potential for medium throughput imaging applications.

Cellular assays for SLC drug targets expressed in organelles, such as Mitoferrin-2, are particularly challenging, because the overexpression of the transporter often leads to altered sub-cellular localization, which may compromise its physiological function (Wang et al., 2020). Plasma membrane redirection of Mitoferrin-2 has been previously described (Dvorak et al., 2021) and might provide convenience for assay development. However, Mitoferrin-2 redirection to the plasma membrane by itself may lead to alteration of cellular iron gradients. In the HEKIM2 cells, Mitoferrin-2 was properly localized to mitochondria, which allowed us to study Mitoferrin-2 iron transport in physiologically relevant cellular compartment.

Furthermore, Mitoferrin-2 expressed in HEKIM2 cells retained its iron transport activity, as demonstrated by increased iron concentrations as detected by ICP-MS analysis in enriched mitochondrial fractions. However, the trace element analysis in enriched mitochondria has its limitations. First, the enrichment procedure used leads to pure fractions, as assessed by Western Blot, but is quite inefficient in terms of yield and requires a large number of cells. Second, mitochondrial trace element analysis by ICP-MS is time-consuming and technically laborious, expensive, and not amenable to high-throughput screening applications. Therefore, we aimed to develop a cell-based assay utilizing RPA as fluorescence readout.

The chemical nature of the RPA sensor and its iron binding properties as an RPA-Fe²⁺ complex (3:1) have been thoroughly described elsewhere (Petrat et al., 2002). Recently, RPA has been successfully used in various studies investigating the role of mitochondrial iron in various disease contexts (Bogacz and Krauth-Siegel, 2018; Chang et al., 2016; Li et al., 2018). Of note, the RPA sensor detects iron concentrations in the low micromolar range (Petrat et al., 2002). As iron source we used Fe(II) SO₄, most likely taken up in cells via DMT-1 (SLC11A2), which is expressed at high levels in the parental HEK293-JumpIn cell line as shown in the RESOLUTE Knowledgebase (Superti-Furga et al., 2020) (<https://re-solute.eu/knowledgebase/gene/SLC11A2>). The utilized concentration of 1–100 μM exogenous iron is in the same range as normal serum iron levels as reflected by levels of iron-bound transferrin (11–32 μM (Pagana et al., 2021)).

Both Mitoferrin-1 and -2 are expressed in HEK293-JumpIn cells. Both proteins share functional characteristics and Mitoferrin-1 can compensate for Mitoferrin-2 deficiency *in vivo* (Seguin et al., 2020). Although our cells express Mitoferrin-1 (<https://re-solute.eu/knowledgebase/gene/SLC25A37>), the strong overexpression of Mitoferrin-2 would dominate the marginal contribution of Mitoferrin-1, as determined in DOX+ HEK293-JI-Mitoferrin-2 cells (TPM of 15 and 1177 for Mitoferrin-1 and -2, respectively; <https://re-solute.eu/resources/dashboards/transcriptomics/analysis/AN008Z-0>). Therefore, we could

assume that most of the observed mitochondrial RPA signal in our assay was generated by Mitoferrin-2. Of note, the generation of a cell line that overexpresses Mitoferrin-2 using a Mitoferrin-1/-2 double-knockout HEK293-JumpIn genetic background as a cell system might further improve the assay window and could be matter of future investigations.

In conclusion, we developed a medium-throughput Mitoferrin-2-mediated iron transport assay, which may be used for screening and identification of modulators of Mitoferrin-2, a potential disease-relevant drug target.

4. Materials and methods

4.1. Cell lines and reagents

The Jump In T-Rex human embryonic kidney 293 cell line (HEK293-JumpIn) with doxycycline-inducible expression of human Mitoferrin-2 (HEK293-JI-Mitoferrin-2) was constructed by the Research Center for Molecular Medicine of the Austrian Academy of Sciences, Medical University of Vienna, Austria (CeMM) as described previously (Sijben et al., 2021). Briefly, HEK293-JI-Mitoferrin-2 cells were generated by transfection of HEK293-JumpIn cells with a vector containing the human SLC25A28 gene with a C-terminal HA tag (pDONR221_SLC25A28; <https://www.addgene.org/132016/>). Dulbecco's modified Eagles medium (DMEM 1X + GlutaMAX + 4.5 g/L Glucose + Pyruvate), G418 were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Darmstadt, Germany). Hank's Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS) and Blastidicin were obtained from ThermoFisher Scientific (Waltham, MA, USA). Rhodamine B[(1,10-phenanthroline-5-yl)-aminocarbonyl]benzyl ester (RPA) was purchased from Squarix GmbH (Marl, Germany), and used according to manufacturer's instructions. All other chemicals used in this study were purchased from commercial resources and were of analytical grade. The HEK293-JI-Mitoferrin-2 cell line used in this study is available at <https://re-solute.eu/resources/reagents> and the respective plasmids are available through Addgene (for more information on the collection, see: <https://www.addgene.org/browse/article/28206712/>).

4.2. Cell culture

HEK293-JumpIn, HEK293-JI-Mitoferrin-2, and HEKIM2 cells were cultured in DMEM supplemented with 10 % fetal calf serum (FCS), 100 μg/mL streptomycin and 100 IU/mL penicillin and split twice weekly to reach approximately 80 % confluency. Prior to each experiment, cells were cultured for two passages in culture medium supplemented with 2 mg/mL G418 and 5 μg/mL Blastidicin to select for Mitoferrin-2-positive cells. When plated for functional assays, cells were grown in regular culture medium without the selection antibiotics.

4.3. Antibodies

For Western blot analyses, the following primary antibodies were purchased and used according to manufacturer's instructions: mouse monoclonal anti-HA Tag (ThermoFisher Scientific Cat. #26183), rabbit monoclonal anti-p70 S6 kinase (Cell Signaling Technology Cat. #2708), rabbit monoclonal anti-Citrate Synthase (Cell Signaling Technology Cat. #14309) and rabbit polyclonal anti-beta Actin (Abcam Cat. ab8227). The following HRP-conjugated secondary antibodies were used: goat anti-mouse (Abcam Cat. ab6789) and goat anti-rabbit (Abcam Cat. 6721). For flow cytometry and immunofluorescence, the AlexaFluor488-conjugated mouse monoclonal anti-HA Tag antibody (ThermoFisher Scientific Cat. #26183-A488) was used.

4.4. Clonal expansion and selection of HEKIM2 cells

HEK293-JI-Mitoferrin-2 cells were serially diluted, after which clonal expansion was carried out in selection antibiotics-containing

medium. The clonal Mitoferrin-2 expression patterns were analyzed using flow cytometry. For this, clones were grown in the presence of doxycycline (DOX+) or of the vehicle (water; DOX-) to induce transgene expression and stained with AF488 labeled-HA Tag antibody. Flow cytometry analysis was performed using a BD FACS Canto machine. The isolated HEK293-JI-Mitoferrin-2-C2 clone (hereafter: HEKiM2) was selected for further experiments.

4.5. Mitochondrial ionomics

HEKiM2 cells were cultured in T175 cell culture flasks to confluency and treated for 24 h with vehicle (water) or doxycycline (1 µg/mL) to induce transgene expression. Mitochondrial iron loading was performed by incubating cells for 24 h in medium with reduced doxycycline (0.01 µg/mL), to avoid doxycycline-mediated chelating effects, 100 µM of an in-house prepared ⁵⁸Fe solution (12 % v/v), and 500 µM of L-ascorbic acid (Sigma Cat. #A7506) as reducing agent. Afterwards, cells were harvested, and mitochondria were isolated a commercially available centrifugation kit (Qiagen Cat. #37612) following manufacturer's instructions for cell lysates. The enriched mitochondrial fractions were supplemented with diluted nitric acid and an internal metal standard mixture and analyzed with ICP-MS using external calibration. Concentrations outside the calibration range were extrapolated.

4.6. Mitoferrin-2 fluorometric cell-based assay for medium-throughput screening

Mitochondrial iron transport was measured utilizing an RPA-based fluorescence readout, with quenching of mitochondrial RPA fluorescence being proportional to mitochondrial Fe(II) concentrations. HEKiM2 cells (55,000 cells/well) were seeded in 100 µL of plating medium in presence of vehicle or doxycycline (1 µg/mL) to induce Mitoferrin-2 expression and grown in poly-D-lysine coated 96-well plates for 24 h. Subsequently, the medium was replaced, and the cells were incubated for 12 h with FCS-free DMEM (100 µg/mL streptomycin and 100 IU/mL penicillin), 0.01 µg/mL doxycycline and 0–100 µM of Fe (II)SO₄:L-ascorbic acid 1:5. Prior to imaging, cells were washed with HBSS, incubated for 20 min at 37 °C, 5 % CO₂ with 1 µM RPA in HBSS, and washed with HBSS to eliminate excess dye. At this concentration, RPA has been shown to be non-toxic (Petrat et al., 2002). Imaging was conducted on a scanR high-content screening station (Olympus, Tokyo, Japan) at an excitation wavelength of 555 nm and emission wavelength bandwidth 600/37 nm.

4.7. Data analysis

All data were analyzed using Graphpad Prism 9.0 (Graphpad software Inc., San Diego, CA, USA). Data are presented as mean ± standard deviation of at least two independent experiments.

For ionomics analyses, isotope concentrations in the isolated mitochondrial fractions were obtained with ICP-MS (Element 2, Thermo Fisher Scientific) and normalized to total protein in the cytosolic fraction. Protein determination was performed using a BCA protein assay kit (ThermoFisher Scientific Cat. #23225).

For image analyses, segmentation and quantification of RPA in cells was performed by using scanR (Olympus, Tokyo, Japan) and Columbus (Perkin Elmer, Waltham, MA, USA) high-content imaging analysis software. Nuclei were segmented, and the nuclear RPA background signal was filtered out of the subsequent analyses.

Statistical analyses were performed using Graphpad Prism 9.0.

Z' is calculated as $Z' = 1 - \frac{3(\sigma_p + \sigma_n)}{|\mu_p - \mu_n|}$

Figures were generated using R 4.2.2.

5. Informed consent statement

Not applicable.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Marcello Polesel: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Matthaus H.E. Wildschut:** Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Cédric Doucerain:** Investigation. **Michael Kuhn:** Formal analysis, Investigation. **Anna Flace:** Investigation. **Leandro Sá Zanetti:** Investigation. **Anna-Lena Steck:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Supervision, Validation. **Maria Wilhelm:** Supervision. **Alvaro Ingles-Prieto:** Funding acquisition, Project administration, Resources, Writing – review & editing. **Tabea Wiedmer:** Funding acquisition, Project administration, Resources. **Giulio Superti-Furga:** Funding acquisition, Project administration, Resources. **Vania Manolova:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Franz Dürrenberger:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: M.P., M.H.E.W., C.D., M.K., A-L.S., M.W., A.F., L.S.Z., V.M. and F.D. are current or past employees of CSL Vifor and may own equities. CSL Vifor is an in-kind contributor of the RESOLUTE consortium.

Data availability

The data presented in this article may be provided by the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mito.2024.101889>.

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